

Kinetics of thermal dehydration and decomposition of hydrated chlorides of some 3d transition metals (Mn-Co series). Part-III. Dehydration and decomposition of CoCl_2 hydrates

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An attempt has been made to study the thermal dehydration behavior of CoCl_2 with different states of hydration in static air as well as in flowing nitrogen atmosphere by TG/DTA method. It is observed that the salt containing more than two moles of water of hydration dehydrates in three steps and only the dihydrate salt dehydrates in two steps losing one mole of H_2O in each step. Because of the variable nature of the loss of H_2O moles in the first step of dehydration, kinetics of this have not been studied. However, the kinetics of the dehydration of the last two moles of H_2O in air as well as in flowing N_2 atmosphere have been studied by using the isoconversion method. While nucleation and/or growth is found to be the best fit model for dehydration in static air, in N_2 atmosphere progress of reactant/product interphase appears to be the most appropriate model. The anhydrous salt is stable up to about 400° above which CoCl_2 decomposes with the formation of spinel oxide (Co_3O_4). The kinetics of decomposition also tends to follow the progress of phase boundary model.

In the two preceding communications¹ on the dehydration of $\text{MnCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{FeCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ it has been observed that the two salts dehydrate in three steps and the anhydrous salts tend to sublimate without undergoing decomposition, especially under the condition of flowing nitrogen. The remaining three hydrated chlorides of the present series of 3d transition metals however undergo either dechlorination or dehydrochlorination in the presence of water vapour to form metal oxides. This property has assumed special importance in recent times in connection with the preparation of pure oxides of desired shape and size using pyrohydrolysis technique². According to this technique concentrated aqueous solution of a suitable metal chloride is sprayed over a heated surface in finely controlled "aerosol" type jet to produce instantaneously granular oxide and HCl or Cl_2 gas which are recovered and reused to generate metal chloride³. The fine oxide particles, generally of spherical shape, are used as valuable raw material in powder metallurgy.

Thermal dehydration of cobalt chloride hydrate has been studied by earlier investigators because of its characteristic color change at different steps of dehydration and therefore find wide use as an indicator for the presence of moisture⁴ in a drying agent like silica gel. Grindstaff and Fogel⁵ have studied the thermodynamics of dehydration of $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ from vapour pressure measurement. Ribas *et al.*⁶ have studied the kinetics of $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ by using both isothermal and non-isothermal methods and like earlier investigators⁴,

have observed that the salt dehydrates with the loss of 4, 1 and 1 moles of H_2O in successive steps. For all the three steps, nucleation and growth has been found to be the rate-controlling mechanism.

We have reported⁷ thermal dehydration and decomposition behavior of CoCl_2 hydrate containing 5.9 and 7.3 moles of H_2O per mole of CoCl_2 . The results suggest that the loss of first four moles of H_2O does not involve any major change in the structural characteristics of the salt. It is the dihydrate salt whose dehydration (or rehydration of anhydrous salt) which brings about major change in the coordination of the two ligands (Cl^- and H_2O) with respect to metal ion. The objectives of this work were three-fold: (i) to have a broad understanding of the dehydration of CoCl_2 with different states of hydration, (ii) to study the kinetics of the dehydration of the last two moles of water, (iii) to study the kinetics of decomposition of the dehydrated salt.

Results and discussion

Dehydration of $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot x\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ($x = 2-6$) by non-isothermal method:

Fig. 1 illustrates typical TG/DTA curves for the dehydration of some CoCl_2 hydrates containing different moles of water of hydration. Tables 1-3 provide the thermoanalytical data derived from TG/DTA curves obtained at different heating rates in static air (self-generated atmosphere)

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Fig. 1. Typical examples of the simultaneous TG/DTA traces of $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in air and $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in air and in nitrogen atmosphere. The hatched areas under the DTA peaks of dihydrate in air are used to estimate heats of dehydration.

and in flowing N_2 conditions. Fig. 1 shows that except the dihydrate salt the hexahydrate and its partially dehydrated varieties lose their water broadly in three steps, besides initial melting. Table 1 gives the relevant data for the dehydration of $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in static air at 2°, 5° and 10°. It can be noted that the first endothermic peak at 56° represents initial melting which is immediately followed by the first step of dehydration wherein about 3.4 moles of H_2O are lost. Though the TG curve of this step does not show any break, the DTA shows two consecutive endo peaks; one at 66–67°, the other at 78–90°. Since the temperature of the first peak varies slightly with heating rate and is also sharp in nature, it is attributed to some physical/phase change, possibly rearrangement in the coordination sphere upon losing about 2 moles of H_2O . The latter peak, however, represents usual endothermic effect due to first step of dehy-

dration.

The second and the third steps of dehydration represent the losses of little more than one mole of H_2O in the temperature ranges 123–133° and 165–177°, respectively.

Table 2 shows the temperature and mass loss data obtained from the simultaneous TG/DTA curves of partially dehydrated salts in static air and flowing N_2 conditions. It is interesting to note from Table 2 that the general nature of the TG/DTA of any intermediate hydrate containing more than two moles of H_2O per mole of CoCl_2 is similar to that of hexa-hydrate salt. The only exception is that the two endothermic peaks at 66° and at 78–90° in the first step of dehydration disappear and only a single peak at temperature 53–55° appears for the loss of about one mole of H_2O in air as shown in Table 2. Only at 4°/min a weak additional endo effect is observed at 64°, possibly due to more water present in this sample. Therefore, initial melting and dehydration occur simultaneously in the first step for intermediate hydrates. Table 2 shows that while the moles of water lost in the first step tend to decrease with increase in heating rate, there is practically no change in the moles of water lost for the 2nd and the 3rd steps of dehydration in air.

In flowing nitrogen atmosphere the separate endothermic peak for dehydration is better resolved in the first step, possibly due to the loss of more water in this step than in static air. That the flowing N_2 facilitates thermal dehydration is evident not only from the loss of more water, but also from lower DTA peak temperature as also observed for the dehydration of MnCl_2 and FeCl_2 hydrates¹. However, the loss of extra water from CoCl_2 hydrate is confined to the first step only as the losses from the 2nd and the 3rd steps remain unchanged at one mole each.

Table 3 provides the DTA/TG data of the dehydration and decomposition of cobalt chloride dihydrate. The interesting feature in the appearance of a weak endothermic effect at 121° before the loss of first mole of water takes place. Though the peak is well-resolved at 5°/min, but becomes weak to very weak with increase in heating rate. It is plau-

Table 1. Effect of heating rate on the DTA/TG parameters of the thermal dehydration of $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in static air

Heating rate °C/min	DTA peak for initial melting °C	1st step of dehydration			2nd step of dehydration			3rd step of dehydration		
		Temp. range (Ti -Tc) °C	DTA* peak °C	Moles of H_2O lost	Temp. range (Ti -Tc) °C	DTA* peak °C	Moles of H_2O lost	Temp. range (Ti -Tc) °C	DTA* peak °C	Moles of H_2O lost
2	56	58–82	66, 78	3.4	108–129	123	1.3	147–170	165	1.2
5	56	59–92	67, 84	3.0	112–140	129	1.4	150–182	174	1.2
10	56	60–110	66, 90	3.4	120–150	133	1.1	150–193	177	1.2

*All the DTA peaks are endothermic.

Table 2. Effect of heating rate on the DTA/TG parameters of the thermal dehydration of $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot x\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ($x = 2.8\text{--}3.5$) in static air and N_2 atmosphere

Heating rate °C/min	1st step of dehydration			2nd step of dehydration			3rd step of dehydration		
	Temp. range (Ti -Tc) °C	DTA* peak °C	Moles of H ₂ O lost	Temp. range (Ti -Tc) °C	DTA* peak °C	Moles of H ₂ O lost	Temp. range (Ti -Tc) °C	DTA* peak °C	Moles of H ₂ O lost
In static air :									
2	40–60	54	0.79	105–131	118	1.18	135–165	154	1.18
4	40–75	53, 64	1.02	112–140	127	1.17	140–180	169	1.24
6	35–65	53	0.40	111–152	133	1.14	152–195	175	1.21
8	38–75	55	0.35	115–166	140	1.19	166–200	182	1.26
In flowing nitrogen atmosphere :									
4	32–70	55	1.46	96–126.5	118	1.09	126.5–167	152.5	1.09
6	32–76	58, 64	1.40	104–135	125	1.10	135–175	160	1.10
8	30–77	58, 64	1.22	103–137	127	1.08	137–180	163	1.08
10	30–85	58, 68	1.23	101–143	132	1.12	142–195	168.5	1.09

*All the DTA peaks are endothermic. Ti = temperature of the inception of DTA peak. Tc = temperature of the completion of DTA peak.

Table 3. Effect of heating rate on the DTA/TG parameters of the thermal dehydration of $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in static air

Heating rate °C/min	1st step of dehydration			2nd step of dehydration			Decomposition		
	Temp. range (Ti -Tc) °C	DTA* peak °C	Moles of H ₂ O lost	Temp. range (Ti -Tc) °C	DTA* peak °C	Moles of H ₂ O lost	Temp. range (Ti -Tc) °C	Mass loss (a) %	Total loss (b) %
5	98–143	121, 131	0.98	143–187	176	1.02	400–660	29.0	50.76
10	110–150	126, 137	0.95	150–220	183	1.02	420–710	27.2	48.70
15	116–160	134, 140	0.92	160–230	193	1.18	450–770	27.3	50.07

(a) Loss between 400° and 800°. (b) Loss between ambient and 800°. All the DTA peaks are endothermic.

sible that the beginning of the process of dehydration is always preceded by certain relaxation of the coordinate bonding of metal ion with water, irrespective of the state of hydration of the salt.

After the removal of water there is a wide temperature gap (plateau) before the decomposition of anhydrous CoCl_2 begins at about 400°. The completion of decomposition is also indicated by a perfectly flat plateau at which mass loss varies between 27.2 and 29.0%. It has been shown in our earlier work⁷ that though the end product at temperature above 700° is Co_3O_4 , intermediate formation of Co_2O_3 at 600° has been indicated by the XRD method. But, because of the presence of undecomposed CoCl_2 the diffraction pattern is not fully conclusive about the occurrence of Co_2O_3 . Further, some authors⁸ have expressed doubts about the occurrence of Co_2O_3 without the presence of CoO . Therefore, dechlorination reaction takes place according to either of the following schemes :

Since the loss of chlorine is directly related to the uptake of oxygen the total loss is required to be calculated with respect to both CoCl_2 and oxygen. Subsequently, by subtracting the percent gain in mass due to oxygen from total mass loss we may get net loss due to chlorine. From eqs. (1) and (2) these values are 30.5 and 27.7%, respectively. While at slow heating rate Co_3O_4 appears to be the main product, at higher heating rates oxidation of CoO remain incomplete and therefore net loss decreases slightly as can be seen from Table 3.

Heats of dehydration of cobalt chloride hydrates :

We have carried out detailed investigation^{7,9} on the estimation of heats of dehydration from the DTA peak areas of the different steps dehydration of CoCl_2 hydrates containing 6–7 moles of H_2O per mole of CoCl_2 . The average ΔH_{dehyd} values of the last two steps of dehydration are 45.6 and 59.7 kJ mol^{-1} respectively. In the present work at least three experiments have been carried out at 10°/min using

partially dehydrated (almost dihydrate) salt. Fig. 1 illustrates the shaded areas under two typical DTA peaks which have been used for the estimation of ΔH_{dehyd} according to the procedure described in one of the preceding papers^{1(a)}. The values are found to be very close giving average values of 25.4 and 26.0 kJ mol⁻¹, respectively. As we have stated in the foregoing section that dehydration of CoCl₂ hydrate is always preceded by certain extent of relaxation/rearrangement of the coordination bonding of the ligands. During predrying at low temperature the salt had enough time to undergo rearrangement of bonding and attain a relatively stable intermediate structure which is unlikely to attain under increasing temperature (non-isothermal) of the fully hydrated salt at 10°/min. Consequently, certain amount of heat is absorbed for the purpose of bond relaxation/rearrangement, before each step of dehydration of the fully hydrated salt, leading to the formation of new product phase. It is therefore natural that ΔH_{dehyd} values of the last two moles of water are higher for the dehydration of hexahydrate than for partly dehydrated salt including dihydrate.

Kinetics of dehydration :

As stated in the beginning of this paper, meaningful results cannot be obtained from the study of the kinetics of the initial or first step of dehydration of CoCl₂ hydrate containing more than two moles of H₂O. This is because of the variable nature of the moles of water lost from this step, besides the occurrence of melting. It is therefore, more worthwhile to study the kinetics of dehydration of the last two moles of H₂O the status of which are more or less similar with respect to cobalt ion.

Fig. 2 shows the fractional mass loss vs temperature for the dehydration of the last two moles of water from partly dehydrated salt at different heating rates. Curves I-III represent loss of last but one mole of H₂O (1st step) and the curves IV-VI represent the loss of last mole of H₂O (2nd

Fig. 2. Plot of fraction dehydrated (α) vs temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) for the two steps of dehydration of $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in air at different heating rates.

step). Figs. 3 and 4 show the corresponding isoconversion plots i.e. plots of log (heating rate) vs reciprocal temperature at different values of α for the two steps. For the 1st step the linear behavior follows in the α range 0.1–0.8 and the activation energy (E , kJ mol⁻¹) values obtained from the slopes are reasonably constant for the α range as given in Table 4. The mean E value is used to calculate θ at the three heating rates according to the procedure described in the 1st part^{1(a)} of this series of papers. The mean values of θ at different conversion levels (α) are given in Table 5.

Fig. 3. Plot of log (heating rate) vs $1/T$ for the first step of dehydration of dihydrate in air at different levels of α .

Fig. 4. Plot of log (heating rate) vs $1/T$ for the second step of dehydration of dihydrate in air at different levels of α .

Table 4. Activation energy (E) values obtained by the isoconversion method for thermal dehydration of $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in static air and flowing N_2 atmosphere

Fraction Dehydrated (α)	Dehydration in static air		Dehydration in N_2 flow atmosphere	
	Loss of 1st mole of H_2O	Loss of 2nd mole of H_2O	Loss of 1st mole of H_2O	Loss of 2nd mole of H_2O
	E values ^a kJ mol^{-1}	E values ^a kJ mol^{-1}	E values ^b kJ mol^{-1}	E values ^b kJ mol^{-1}
0.05	–	–	127.4	–
0.10	91.01	72.80	131.1	–
0.20	88.40	68.25	131.1	101.9
0.30	91.01	67.34	136.5	103.8
0.40	91.01	68.25	132.9	109.2
0.50	88.40	67.34	127.4	100.1
0.60	88.40	61.88	122.0	103.8
0.70	84.63	59.22	112.9	103.8
0.80	100.10	60.06	109.2	111.0
0.90	–	60.06	–	100.1
0.95	–	–	–	91.0
Mean E	90.37	65.02	125.6	102.7

^aComprising heating rates of 2°, 4° and 6°/min. ^bComprising heating rates of 4°, 6° and 8°/min.

Table 5. Average values of reduced time (θ) calculated from three heating rates using the mean E values given in Table 4 for thermal dehydration of $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$

Fraction dehydrated (α)	Dehydration in static air		Dehydration in N_2 atmosphere	
	Loss of 1st mole of H_2O $\times 10^{12}$ min	Loss of 2nd mole of H_2O $\times 10^8$ min	Loss of 1st mole of H_2O $\times 10^{17}$ min	Loss of 2nd mole of H_2O $\times 10^{12}$ min
0.05	–	–	1.410	–
0.10	3.712	5.297	1.730	–
0.20	4.166	5.875	2.255	0.048
0.30	4.759	6.504	2.838	0.503
0.40	5.354	7.023	3.445	0.601
0.50	6.049	7.523	4.126	0.711
0.60	6.810	8.123	4.966	0.832
0.70	7.638	8.800	6.019	0.988
0.80	9.493	9.664	7.387	1.154
0.90	–	10.810	–	1.466
0.95	–	–	–	1.669

The values are used to calculate^{1(a)} real time t required to attain different levels of α at 390, 400 and 410 K. The mechanistic model that fits the data best is FI i.e. rapid nucleation with slow growth. The results are given in Table 6.

For the loss of last mole of H_2O the isoconversion plots show good linear relationship from $\alpha = 0.1$ to 0.9 (see Fig. 4). Following the procedure as described above it has been observed that the Avrami-Erofeev equation (see Table 4,

Ref. 1(a)) of nucleation and growth with $m = 2$ fits the data (θ or t vs α) best. The last two steps of dehydration of $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in static air are in excellent agreement, not only with respect to the E values but also the mechanistic model as found by Ribas *et al.*⁶.

Fig. 5a depicts the plot of α vs T at different heating rates for the loss of first mole of H_2O from dihydrate in flowing N_2 atmosphere. The corresponding isoconversion plots Fig. 5b demonstrate that while good linear behavior is

Table 6. Kinetic models and Arrhenius parameters derived from isothermal time at different α values for the dehydration and decomposition of $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$

Steps of dehydration	Average θ range (min)	α range	Temp. range (K)	Kinetic model (code)	Correlation coefficient (R^2)	Arrhenius parameters		
						E (kJ mol ⁻¹)	log A (min ⁻¹)	Correl. coeff. (R^2)
Dehydration in static air :								
Loss of 1st mole of H_2O	(3.712–9.493) $\times 10^{-12}$	0.1–0.8	390–410	$F1$	0.9967	90.3	11.42	1.0
Loss of 2nd mole of H_2O	(5.297–10.810) $\times 10^{-8}$	0.1–0.9	420–440	$A2$	0.9993	65.0	7.93	1.0
Dehydration in N_2 flow atmosphere :								
Loss of 1st mole of H_2O	(1.410–7.387) $\times 10^{-17}$	0.05–0.8	380–390	$R3$	0.9991	125.6	15.84	1.0
Loss of 2nd mole of H_2O	(0.408–1.669) $\times 10^{-12}$	0.2–0.95	420–440	$R3$	0.9994	101.3	11.48	1.0
Decomposition of dihydrate salt (isothermal experiment) :								
		0.02–0.88	673–873	$R2$	–	55.2	1.26	0.9905
		–	–	$R3$	–	53.6	1.50	0.9901

observed for 4°, 6° and 8°/min the data for 10°/min show sharp deviation and therefore not shown in Fig. 5b. The average E value of 125.6 kJ mol⁻¹ is higher than that observed for the corresponding loss in static air condition (Table 4). The mechanistic model that fits the isothermal data best is the progress of the product phase boundary with spherical symmetry ($R3$) that is from periphery to the centre.

Fig. 6a illustrates the plot of α vs T at different heating rates for the loss of last mole of H_2O from dihydrate salt in flowing N_2 atmosphere. The corresponding isoconversion plots in Fig. 6b shows linear behavior comprising 4°, 6° and 8°/min of heating rates at $\alpha = 0.2$ –0.95. The average E value of 103 kJ mol⁻¹ for the above range of α is also higher than the corresponding step of dehydration in static air (Table 4). The E values appear to be intriguing because flowing nitrogen accelerates the rate of dehydration and therefore E values are expected to decrease in N_2 flow condition. To examine the validity of this observation, Kissinger's¹⁰ method has been used to determine apparent E values from the variation of DTA peak temperature with heating rate. The equations are as follows :

when the order of the reaction (n) $\neq 1$

$$\log [b/Tm^2] = \log \{ (A R/E) n (1 - \alpha_m)^{n-1} \} - E/2.3 RT \quad (3)$$

when $n = 1$

$$\log [b/Tm^2] = \log \{ (AR/E) \} - E/2.3 RT \quad (4)$$

where, b = heating rate, Tm = DTA peak temperature (K),

α_m = fractional mass loss at Tm , A = pre-exponential factor (min⁻¹) and R = molar gas constant.

The plot of $\log (b/Tm^2)$ vs $1/Tm$ should yield straight line irrespective of the order of reaction as shown in Fig. 7. The apparent E values for the two steps of dehydration in air are 78.9 and 67.7 kJ mol⁻¹ respectively which are close to those determined by the isoconversion method (Table 4). However, in flowing N_2 the apparent E values for the two steps are 86.2 and 83.7 kJ mol⁻¹, respectively. Though these values are lower than those obtained by the isoconversion method, but are higher than those observed for static air confirming that, in the case of dehydration of $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, inert gas flow does not bring about reduction in activation energy value of the process.

Kinetics of isothermal decomposition :

Since the isoconversion method is found to be not applicable at high heating rates, the kinetics of decomposition can not be studied by this method. Therefore, only isothermal method has been used for the study of the kinetics of decomposition of the dihydrate salt.

The decomposition of the salt is quite slow at 400 and 450° as is also evident from the TG trace in Fig. 1. Above 450° the rate of decomposition increases and is very rapid at 600°. After 60 min of heating at this temperature the loss of chlorine is about 26% corresponding to the total loss of about 54%, suggesting that the salt contains about 2 moles of water of hydration (Fig. 8). Since at higher temperature decomposition begins instantaneously both dechlorination

Fig. 5. (a) Plot of α vs temperature (T) in Kelvin for the first step of dehydration of dihydrate at different heating rates in nitrogen atmosphere. (b) The corresponding plot of \log (heating rate) vs $1/T$ at different levels of α .

and dehydrochlorination may take place through the possible formation of oxychloride as observed for the chlorides of Cu and Zn¹¹. The overall reaction for a salt with x moles of H_2O is as follows :

This shows that loss of either Cl or HCl is independent of the state of hydration of the salt. The stoichiometry of the reaction suggests that the combined loss of Cl and HCl is 27% after the correction of mass gain due to uptake of oxygen. The combined loss of Cl and HCl was noted at an interval of 0.25% with respect to time and temperature. These values when divided by the total combined loss (calculated) of 27% give the fractional loss (α) for decomposition. It is observed that the mechanistic model which fits the α -time data best is the progress of the reactant/product phase boundary with either cylindrical ($R2$) or spherical ($R3$) symmetry.

Fig. 6. (a) Plot of α vs (T) for the second step of dehydration of dihydrate at different heating rates in nitrogen atmosphere. (b) The corresponding plot of \log (heating rate) vs $1/T$ at different levels of α .

Fig. 7. Plot of $\log (b/T_m^2)$ vs $1/T_m$ according to Kissinger equation for the dehydration of dihydrate under different environments.

Fig. 8. Plot of percent chlorine lost with respect to initial mass vs time of calcination at different temperatures.

Since, the Arrhenius plots show slightly higher correlation coefficient for R2 model it may be accepted as more appropriate. The apparent E and $\log A$ values are given Table 6.

Experimental

Materials : About 15 g of freshly procured A.R. grade $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (M/s Qualigen Fine Chemicals, India) was ground in an agate mortar to finer than $100 \mu\text{m}$, transferred to a wide mouth sample bottle and stored in a desiccator during which the water of hydration fell to 5.7–5.8 per mole of CoCl_2 . An attempt was made to prepare dihydrate by drying 7–8 g ground hexahydrate salt in an air oven at $50 \pm 2^\circ$ until violet-blue color was obtained. To check the composition of the product during drying, an accurately weighed amount (~ 0.2 g) was dissolved in water and analysed for Co and Cl^- contents. By careful adjustment of the period of drying it was possible to attain the composition very close to dihydrate. However, after a few days of storage even in the desiccator the dried sample tends to gain some moisture and therefore increases to 3.0–3.5 moles of water.

Methods : The simultaneous DTA/TG experiments were carried out in a Shimadzu-DT-40 (Japan) Thermal analyzer according to the procedure described earlier^{1(a)}. The isothermal decomposition of the dihydrate salt was carried out in a tubular furnace of 40 cm length and 3.75 cm internal diameter with maximum heating zone of about 20 cm at the center of the furnace. The temperature was maintained at $\pm 2^\circ$ with the help of a PID controller (Shimadzu, Japan). About 0.15 g accurately weighed dihydrate salt was transferred to a series of quartz boats of 6 cm in length. The

sample was uniformly spread in the boat so that the thickness of the bed never exceeded 2 mm. The furnace was heated to the requisite temperature and when the reasonable steady state was attained, one boat at a time was introduced into the furnace. From that moment the time of heating was reckoned. The tip of the thermocouple (Pt, 10% Ir) leading to the temperature controller was in contact with the bottom of the boat. After the specified period of heating the boat was withdrawn from the furnace, cooled in a desiccator and weighed. The extent of decomposition was estimated by leaching the total calcined mass in water for about 30 min at $60\text{--}70^\circ$. The insoluble residue was separated by filtration and the total volume of the filtrate was made up to 100 ml. In suitable aliquots Co and Cl^- contents were estimated taking suitable aliquots. From the difference between initial and final amounts of Cl^- present in the sample, percent loss with respect to initial mass can be obtained. Loss of chlorine can also be estimated from the difference between initial and final Co contents. These two values sometimes differ by 0.4–0.5% and therefore mean value is taken.

Analysis : Cobalt was analyzed by titration with 0.01 M EDTA at pH about 6.0 using xylenol orange as indicator. But when present in very small quantity Co was estimated by atomic absorption spectrophotometry (AAS). Chlorine was estimated by titration with 0.01 M AgNO_3 solution using K_2CrO_4 as indicator.

References

1. (a) S. B. Kanungo, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2004, **81**, 644; (b) 2004, **81**, 750.
2. H. Jedlicka, 'Proc. Symp. Chloride Hydrometallurgy', Brussels, 1977, 182; H. N. Sinha and J. R. Tufley, "Extractive Metallurgy '81", The Institute of Mining and Metallurgy, London, 1981, p. 421; G. van Weert and E. M. L. Peck, *Hydrometallurgy*, 1992, **29**, 513.
3. T. Q. Lin, Q. Sakurai, N. Mizutani and M. Kate, *J. Materials Sci.*, 1986, **21**, 698; S. Stopic, I. Ilic and D. Ushkovic, *J. Sci. Sintering*, 1994, **28**, 145.
4. E. L. Simmons and W. W. Wendlandt, *Thermochim. Acta*, 1971, **31**, 25 and references cited therein.
5. W. K. Grindstaff and N. Fogel, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1972, 1476.
6. J. Ribas, A. Escuer, M. Serra and R. Vicente, *Thermochim. Acta*, 1986, **102**, 125.
7. S. K. Mishra and S. B. Kanungo, *J. Thermal Anal.*, 1992, **37**, 2437.
8. F. A. Cotton and G. Wilkinson, "Advanced Inorganic Chemistry", 3rd. ed., Wiley Eastern Ltd., New Delhi, 1990, p. 876.
9. S. B. Kanungo and S. K. Mishra, *Metals Materials and Processes*, 1997, **9**, 1.
10. H. E. Kissinger, *Anal. Chem.*, 1959, **29**, 1702.
11. M. C. Ball and R. F. M. Coultard, *J. Chem. Soc.(A)*, 1968, 1417.